

Impact Behaviour of Quasi-Isotropic CFRP Laminate

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ABSTRACT

The effects of loading rate on the impact behaviour of quasi-isotropic $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_{2S,4T}$ CFRP has been studied with edge wise Charpy V notched specimen using static and instrumented Charpy impact tests. The peak load and flexural modulus increased slightly with increasing the loading rate, then decreased with further increase of loading rate. The pronounced decrement of flexural modulus in the dynamic loading region was found to be directly responsible to the rapid increment of both fracture initiation and total fracture energies in this region. Consequently it is suggested that the effects of loading rate on the impact behaviour may be caused by the reduction of compression zone.

INTRODUCTION

The high specific strength and stiffness of carbon/fibre epoxy composites offers a great attraction as an aerospace and conventional structural material, however, the inherent anisotropic mechanical properties and high susceptibility to the impact loading restrict its widescale use of this material. Currently the idea of multiangle laminate, hybrid laminate and the blend of these two have been introduced to overcome these deficiencies despite a fall in strength and stiffness.

The response history of composites specimen subjected to quasi static and dynamic three point flexural loading, i.e. load-displacement curve, is known to be a complex function of following.

- a) Characteristics of constituent lamina
- b) specimen geometry,
lamina angle, thickness, span to depth ratio
presence of notch
- c) testing condition
loading rate, testing temperature and environment

In the present work the influence of loading rate on the static and dynamic response of edge wise quasi isotropic $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_{2S,4T}$ CFRP lamina are studied. The subscript 2S indicates two symmetric and 4T indicates the laminate composed of 4 sets of laminate.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The specimen was made from Courtauld treated fibre with YD-128 epoxy and TETA. The laminate with fibre volume fraction of 55% was produced by hot pressing in a matched mould followed by three hours of post curing. A standard Charpy V notched specimen of Fig. 1 were used for both static and dynamic tests.

Fig. 1. Dimension CVN specimen

The quasi static three point flexural tests were conducted in an Instron with 5×10^{-1} , 1×10^1 , 1×10^2 and 5×10^2 mm/min crosshead speeds. The load displacement curve was recorded on the Instron chart recorder except 5×10^2 mm/min cross-head speed, where the Rapicorder was used to record the fast response.

The dynamic tests were conducted with Instrumented Charpy impact testing machine. The striker velocity was controlled to give 8.8×10^4 , 1.7×10^5 and 3×10^5 mm/min by adjusting the angle of striker. Fig. 2 shows the block diagram of experimental set up.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of experimental set up.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flexural modulus of laminate

The response history of specimen subjected to the impact loading is conveniently partitioned into three regions as 1) pre-initial fracture, 2) initial fracture and 3) post fracture (crack propagation).

The pre-initial fracture behaviour under this testing condition is governed by the specimen compliance which is determined by the ratio of tensile and compressive moduli. In practice the flexural modulus is commonly calculated using experimentally determined mid span deflection and applied load by

$$E_f = \frac{(P/\delta)S^2}{48 L} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where P is the applied load, δ , the mid span deflection, L, the moment of inertia and S, the span of the beam.

Recently Adams and Miller (1,2) has shown that the transverse shear strain to give a significant influence on the deflection of the beam under flexural loading. By comparing the flexural modulus, E_f , calculated from eq. (1) with

E_{f1} calculated from classical anisotropic laminate plate theory (for the flat wise specimen), where the transverse shear strain and poison effects are ignored, they found a substantial difference between these two moduli.

Since in their work the flexural modulus for flat wise specimen was considered, the flexural modulus for edge wise specimen E_{f11} has been calculated using classical anisotropic laminate plate theory in this work (3).

$$E_{f11} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n E_h I_k}{I} \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

where E_h and I_k are the flexural modulus and moment of inertia of Kth ply in the laminate respectively.

The values of E_f and E_{f11} were compared in Table 1 and it is noticeable that E_{f11} remained constant regardless of the loading rate, while E_f decreased markedly with increasing the loading rate especially in the dynamic region.

loading rate mm/min	Flexural Modulus	
	$E_f \times 10^3$	$E_{f11} \times 10^3$
5×10^{-1}	8.6	3.2
1×10^1	"	3.6
1×10^2	"	3.4
5×10^2	"	2.8
8.8×10^4	"	1.1
1.7×10^5	"	0.85
3.0×10^5	"	0.6

The dependence of peak load and flexural load on the loading rate are shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. The peak load vs. loading rate

Fig. 4. The Flexural modulus vs. loading rate

The peak load increased slightly as the loading rate increased, showing the maximum at 8.8×10^4 mm/min, then declined moderately with further increase in the loading, i.e. dynamic region. However, the decrease markedly in the flexural modulus commenced from 1×10^1 mm/min loading rate.

The moderate decrease of apparent bending stress and the rates of h_c/t were observed in the unidirectional CFRP lamina during three point bending test. (loading rate between 5×10^1 and 5×10^2 mm/min). h_c denotes the compression zone and h denotes the beam thickness, and the measurements of h_c was made from direct SEM observation of bracture surface (4).

As mentioned in the preceeding section the pre-initial fracture behaviour is governed by the specimen compliance which is determined by the ratio of compression and tension moduli. If we extend the implication of previous observation, (4) the decrease of h_c/h with increasing loading rate arise from the decrease in the h_c (compression zone), hence we can conclude that the decrease of flexural modulus in the dynamic region was caused by the reduction of compressive zone.

Fracture Energy of Laminate

The fracture initiation and total fracture energies were obtained by integrating the area under load-displacement curve to the peak load and total fracture respectively. Figs. 5 and 6 shows the variation of both intiation and total fracture energies with the loading rate. Both energies remained constant in the static loading region, however, they increased markedly in the dynamic region.

Fig. 5. Fracture initiation energy vs loading rate

Fig. 6. Total fracture energy vs loading rate.

Considering the results in Figs. 3 and 4, the moderate decrease of peak load and pronounced decrease of flexural modulus were clearly observed in the dynamic loading region. The rapid increment of both fracture energies with loading rate in the dynamic loading rate are attributed to the decrease in the flexural modulus, which is associated with the reduction of compressive zone during impact loading.

CONCLUSION

The flexural modulus of quasi isotropic $(0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ)_{2S,4T}$ CFRP laminate decreased rapidly with increasing the loading rate in the dynamic impact loading region. The analysis has shown that the transverse shear strain give a significant contribution to the reduction of flexural modulus.

The rapid increase of both fracture initiation and total fracture energies in the dynamic loading rate region is a consequence of rapid decrement of the flexural modulus.

The observed effects of loading rate on the loading response of $(0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ)_{2S,4T}$ laminate may be associated with the variation of compression zone in the beam subjected to the flexural loading.

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